

KNOWLEDGE LEVEL OF TURMERIC GROWERS ABOUT BIOFERTILIZERS

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. (MS Received: 17.01.2023; MS Revised:18.02.2023; MS Accepted: 19.03.2023)

MS 2996

(RESEARCH PAPER IN EXTENSION EDUCATION.)

Abstract

Present study was conducted in Wasmat block of Hingoli district of Maharashtra as it is a turmeric growing tract with the objectives to know the profiles of the turmeric growers and to assess the knowledge level of turmeric growers. 120 turmeric growers from 10 villages were randomly selected for study. An interview schedule seeking information of the turmeric growers with respect personal characteristics and knowledge about biofertilizer use was designed for the study. Data revealed that majority of turmeric growers were middle aged, educated up to higher secondary education, had medium land holding, income, social participation, extension contact and risk orientation. 61.67 per cent of the turmeric growers were having medium level of overall knowledge of biofertilizer use. Whereas, 31.67 per cent and 6.66 per cent of turmeric growers were having low- and high-level knowledge, respectively.

Key Words: Knowledge, Turmeric Growers, Biofertilizers

Introduction

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L) is widely used as a spice in South Asia and Middle Eastern Cooking. Turmeric is an important ancient spice and ingredient of Indian dishes. Its use in India as culinary spice and in religious functions dates back in Vedic culture. It is grown in India from times immemorial. India is the world's largest producer, consumer and exporter of turmeric. India produces 80% of global turmeric production and exports 60 percent of worlds export. Telangana is largest producer of turmeric followed by Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Orissa, West Bengal and Maharashtra (Anonymous 2020).

It contains about 69.49% carbohydrates, 6.30% proteins, 5.00% fats and 3.50% minerals and other important elements on dry weight basis. (Swain *et al.*, 2007). Turmeric also contains up to 5.10% essential oils and up to 5% curcumin. Turmeric has anti-inflammatory, carminative, anti-flatulent, antimicrobial, anti-tumor, antioxidant, anti-arthritis, anti-amyloid, anti-ischemic and anti-inflammatory properties. (Singh *et al.*, 2017). It is claimed to be as an immunity boosting, stomachic tonic, blood purifier, antiseptic, anti-acidic and carminative. It is used in wide range from ayurvedic medicines to modern medicines, colours, indicators, cosmetics and dyes. It is regarded in Hindu religion as sacred item for use in ceremonial and religious function.

Crop production depends on use of quality inputs. Though the use of chemical fertilizer played a significant role in increasing crop production, its continuous use deteriorated soil fertility, destroyed soil microbial activity and disturbed environmental and ecological balance. Biofertilizers are believed to be the potential alternative to chemical fertilizers in improvement of soil fertility for sustainable crop production. Biofertilizer's production is also simple, requires less energy, capital and labour force as compared to chemical fertilizers. (Raimi *et al.* 2017).

There is yield gap between productivity of turmeric at farmer's field and its genetic production potential. As biofertilizers plays vital role in turmeric production, the present study was undertaken with the specific objectives to study the socio-economic characteristics of the turmeric growers and to assess their knowledge level towards use of biofertilizers.

Materials And Methods

Hingoli is one of the leading turmeric producer districts in Marathwada region of the Maharashtra State. Present study was purposively conducted in Wasmat block a turmeric growing tract of Hingoli district. 120 turmeric growers from 10 villages were randomly selected, who has cultivated turmeric crop on more than 0.20 ha area. An interview schedule including relevant questions for seeking information with respect personal characteristics of the turmeric growers and their knowledge level about biofertilizer use was designed for the study. Data were collected by contacting the selected turmeric growers at

their homes or farm. The collected data was analyzed, classified and tabulated. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation were used to interpret findings and draw conclusions

Results And Discussion**Profiles of the turmeric growers**

The data with regards to profiles of the turmeric growers is presented in table 1. Results of the table 1 revealed that majority (67.50 percent) of the turmeric growers were middle aged, where as 19.17 per cent and 13.33 per cent turmeric growers belonged to old age group and young age group respectively.

With concern to education, it was observed that 27.50 per cent of the turmeric growers were educated up to higher secondary education followed by 23.33 per cent turmeric growers had 5th to 7th standard primary education, 14.16 per cent had secondary education, 10.83 per cent were illiterate and an equal percentage of turmeric growers had up to 4th standard primary education. 8.33 per cent turmeric growers were graduates, 02.52 per cent were post graduate and 02.50 per cent could able to read and write.

In case of land holding data revealed that 49.16 per cent of the turmeric growers had medium size of land holding followed by 20.00 per cent had marginal land holding. 19.17 percent turmeric growers were small land holder, 11.67 percent were semi medium land holder and none of the respondent had large land holding.

It was observed that majority (45.83%) of turmeric growers were engaged in farming occupation, whereas, 25.00 per cent of turmeric growers engaged in farming with labour, 12.50 per cent turmeric growers engaged in farming with subsidiary occupation, 11.67 per cent of turmeric growers were engaged in farming with business and 5.00 per cent turmeric growers were engaged in farming with service occupation.

It could be seen from Table-1, that 62.50 per cent of turmeric growers had medium income followed by 24.17 per cent and 13.33 per cent turmeric growers had high and low annual income respectively.

Results of Table-1 also revealed that, 58.33 per cent of the turmeric growers were having medium social participation followed by 30.83 per cent and 10.84 per cent turmeric growers had low and high social participation, respectively.

With regards extension contact more than half (52.50%) turmeric growers were having medium level of extension contact. Whereas, 30.83 percent turmeric growers were having low extension contact and only 16.67 per cent had high level of extension contact.

It is observed from Table-1, that more than half (66.67%) turmeric growers had medium level risk orientation whereas, 26.67 and 6.66 per cent of them had low and high level risk orientation respectively.

Table-1. Distribution of the turmeric growers according to their characteristics

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Turmeric growers	
		Number	Per cent
	Age		
1.	Young (up to 29 years)	16	13.33
2.	Middle age (30 to 50 years)	81	67.50
3.	Old (51 and above)	23	19.17
	Mean = 39.45 SD = 10.25		
	Education		
1.	Illiterate	13	10.83
2.	Literate (can only read and write)	03	2.50
3.	Primary education (up to 4th std)	13	10.83
4.	Primary education (5th - 7th std)	28	23.33
5.	Secondary education (8th - 10th std)	17	14.16
6.	Higher secondary education (11th & 12th)	33	27.50
7.	Graduate (above 12th)	10	8.33
8.	Post Graduate	03	2.52
	Land holding		
1.	Marginal (Up to 1 ha.)	24	20.00
2.	Small (1.01 to 2.00 ha.)	23	19.17
3.	Semi medium (2.01 to 4.00 ha.)	14	11.67
4.	Medium (4.01 to 10.00 ha)	59	49.16
5.	Large (10.01 and above)	0	0.00
	Occupation		
1.	Farming	55	45.83
2.	Farming + Labour	30	25.00
3.	Farming + Subsidiary Occupation	15	12.50
4.	Farming + Business	14	11.67
5.	Farming + Service	06	05.00
	Annual Income		
1.	Low (Up to Rs.85729)	29	24.17
2.	Medium (Rs.85730 to255520)	75	62.50
3.	High (Rs. 255521 and above)	16	13.33
	Mean = 1,70,625 SD = 84896		
	Social Participation		
1.	Low (Up to 5)	37	30.83
2.	Medium (6 to 13)	70	58.33
3.	High (14 and above)	13	10.84
	Mean = 8.91 SD = 4.07		
	Extension Contact		
1.	Low (up to 13)	37	30.83
2.	Medium (14 to 21)	63	52.50
3.	High (22 and above)	20	16.67
	Mean = 17.21 SD= 4.78		
	Risk Orientation		
1.	Low (up to 12)	32	26.67
2.	Medium (13 to 23)	80	66.67
3.	High (24 and above)	08	6.66
	Mean = 17.51 SD = 6.00		

1. Knowledge of turmeric growers about Biofertilizers
2. 2.1 Knowledge of turmeric growers about specific aspects of Biofertilizers

Table-2 : Knowledge of turmeric growers about specific aspects of Biofertilizers

N=120

Sr. No.	Specific knowledge about biofertilizers	Knowledge level	
		Frequency	Percent
1.	Production increases due to the use of biofertilizers.	106	88.33
2.	Information about Rhizobium is biofertilizer.	83	69.16
3.	Information about Azospirillum is biofertilizer.	45	37.50
4.	Information about PSB is biofertilizer.	40	33.33

5.	Information about Azotobacter is biofertilizer.	79	65.83
6.	Information about availability of Biofertilizers are at Agricultural University's.	105	87.50
7.	Biofertilizers are used for seed treatment.	69	57.50
8.	For turmeric crop, azospirillum, phosphobacteria and azotobacter biofertilizers are used.	56	46.66
9.	Information about dose of biofertilizers	38	31.66
10.	Information about seed treatment of turmeric with biofertilizers	41	34.16
11.	Information about application of biofertilizers through drip irrigation.	49	40.83
12.	Information about application of biofertilizers through soil by mixing it with FYM/compost.	17	14.16
13.	Information about time of application of biofertilizers.	72	60.00
14.	Use of biofertilizers enhances nitrogen and phosphorus availability.	98	81.66
15.	Information about cost of biofertilizers.	12	10.00

Results of table 2 indicates that majority of turmeric growers (88.33%) had knowledge that production increases due to the application of biofertilizers followed by 87.50 percent turmeric growers were having knowledge about availability of biofertilizers are at Agricultural University's. 81.66 percent were having knowledge about use of biofertilizers enhances nitrogen and phosphorus availability. Table 2 also indicated that 69.16 percent, 65.83 percent, 37.50 percent and 33.33 percent turmeric growers had knowledge about biofertilizers Rhizobium, Azotobacter, Azospirillum and PSB, respectively. 46.66 percent turmeric growers were having knowledge azospirillum, phosphobacteria and azotobacter biofertilizers are used for turmeric crop, 60.00 percent had knowledge about time of application, 57.52 percent turmeric growers had knowledge about seed treatment with biofertilizers. 40.83 percent had knowledge about application of biofertilizers through drip irrigation, 34.16 percent had knowledge about process of seed treatment of turmeric with biofertilizers, 31.66

percent had knowledge about dose of biofertilizers,. Only 14.16 percent and 10.00 percent had knowledge about application of biofertilizers through soil by mixing it with FYM/compost and cost of biofertilizers, respectively.

2.2 Overall knowledge of the turmeric growers about Biofertilizers

Results of Table-3 revealed that 61.67 per cent of turmeric growers belong to medium level of knowledge, whereas 31.67 per cent and 6.66 per cent of turmeric growers were in low- and high-level knowledge category, respectively. The possible reasons for some of the turmeric growers to be in low level of knowledge category is some aspects of biofertilizer technology involved difficult technical aspects which might have come in the way of acquiring needed information. This was also due to difference in personal attributes of the turmeric growers. The findings were in conformity of Borkar (2000).

Table-3. Distribution of the turmeric growers according to their overall knowledge

Sr. No.	Category	Turmeric growers	
		Number	Per cent
1.	Low (Up to 6)	38	31.67
2.	Medium (7 to 10)	74	61.67
3.	High (11 and above)	08	6.66
	Total	120	100.00
	Mean = 8.05	SD = 2.00	

Summery And Conclusions

Profiles of the turmeric growers, it was found majority (67.50 percent) were middle aged, 27.50 per cent were educated up to higher secondary education. Nearly half (49.16 per cent) had medium size of land holding, majority (45.83%) were engaged in farming occupation, 62.50 per cent had medium income, 58.33 per cent were having medium social participation, more than half (52.50%) were having medium level of extension contact and more than half (66.67%) turmeric growers had medium level risk orientation.

Knowledge of turmeric growers about specific aspects of Biofertilizers found that majority of turmeric growers (88.33%) had knowledge that production increases due to the application of biofertilizers followed by 87.50 percent turmeric growers were having knowledge about availability of biofertilizers are at Agricultural University's.

Overall knowledge of the turmeric growers about Biofertilizers observed that 61.67 per cent of turmeric growers belong to medium level of knowledge,

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